

Academic engagement and grit as correlates of academic burnout among form three students in Nyandarua county, Kenya

DAVID GICHOMO^{1a}, DR. JAMES OLUOCH^{2b}, DR. SUSAN NGUNU^{3c}

¹ Master student, Department of Educational psychology, Kenyatta University, Kenya

^{2,3} Lecturer, Department of Educational psychology, Kenyatta University, Kenya

Contact Details: ^a davidgichomo@gmail.com, ^b oluchjames620@gmail.com, ^c Suengunu@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Academic burnout is a condition that arises from students' feeling of exhaustion and incompetence in academics. The academic burnout might be due to multiple factors such as school assignments, continuous assessment tests among other examinations. These may lead to academic disinterest and students' unexplained absenteeism. This study intended to establish the relationship between academic engagement and academic burnout among form three students in Kipipiri Sub-county in Nyandarua County, Kenya. Students experiencing academic burnout may face maladjustment that may seriously affect their academic path. Students in Nyandarua County secondary schools experience academic burnout. The aim of this study therefore, was to determine the relationship between academic engagement and academic burnout. Work engagement theory was used to guide this study. Correlation research design was employed. Form three students were the target population 1,152 (572 boys and 580 girls) from 8 secondary schools in Kipipiri Sub-county. The sampling methods that were used in the study are purposive sampling, proportionate sampling and simple random sampling. The sample comprised of 349 participants from 8 secondary schools. Research tools used consisted of the Utrecht work engagement scale meant for students and academic burnout scale. A pilot study was carried out using 36 students selected randomly in one of the schools within Kipipiri Sub-county. To ascertain validity of the research instrument, the researcher presented them to expert (supervisors) for scrutiny. Cronbach's alpha coefficient was used to ascertain the reliability of the research instruments. Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS version 25) was used to compute inferential and descriptive statistic. The study established that there exists a significant negative relationship between academic engagement and academic burnout. $r(345) = -.68, p < .05$. The study recommended that teachers should come up with guidance programs and other more relevant interventions to help students boost their academic engagement in order to reduce academic burnout.

Keywords : Academic Burnout; Academic Engagement

INTRODUCTION

Worldwide, academic burnout is a major challenge in education as it affects motivation energy of students and deters them from fully engaging in academic work. Academic burnout refers to students' feeling of exhaustion emanating from study demands. Academic burnout leads to students feeling of a sense of academic incompetent, unwilling to do assignments and being pessimistic. Such feeling leads to students developing negative attitude towards learning and school related work (Cillier et al. 2017). Students experiencing academic burnout may have problem of maintaining attendances in classroom, low interest to participate in class activities, feeling of inadequacy in learning academic materials and increased school dropout (Maroco et al. 2020). In Italy for instance, Fiorilli et al. (2017) reported that academic burnout is more common among adolescent students with the symptoms of academic disengagement and exhaustion leading to higher academic procrastination and low performance in academics.

In Nigeria, Eseudu et al. (2019) reported that students with academic burnout exhibit characteristics of high emotional exhaustion and low academic efficacy that leads to academic disengagement. Similarly in Uganda, Kajjimu et al. (2021) reported that 54% of students pursuing medical clinical degree in selected universities had high academic exhaustion, low level of academic efficacy and high level of cynicism.

In Kenya, a study on academic burnout carried out among selected medical schools by Ogoma (2020), reported that many students in the field of medicine were much affected by academic burnout. Oyoo et al. (2020) indicated that academic burnout affect academic achievement negatively. In addition, Winga et al. (2016) found out that students with low academic performance have reduced academic efficacy, high academic exhaustion and disengagement.

Globally, studies that have been done have linked academic engagement with academic burnout. Academic engagement refers to positive and fulfilling state of mind manifested by vigor, absorption and dedication during studying activities. Srivastava et al. (2021) in India found out that academic engagement negatively correlates with academic burnout. In addition, academic engagement among students can be categorized in terms of high, moderate or low and each category affect students' academic burnout differently.

In Africa, Studies on academic engagement in relation to academic burnout have concentrated more on university students. Brittany et al. (2019) in Nigeria revealed that students in social work courses experienced high academic burnout due to high demand encountered during this course. Academic engagement was found to be having a negative relationship with academic burnout. Students with low academic burnout were reported to be having high academic vigor, dedication and absorption.

In Kenya, studies that correlate academic engagement and academic burnout are sparse. Most studies are on academic engagement and how it correlates with academic achievement (Sulum, 2018; Masila & Ileri, 2022). In Nyandarua County there are limited studies if any that have been carried out on academic engagement in relation to academic burnout. Therefore, this research was conducted with an aim of establishing the extent to which academic engagement correlates with academic burnout among students in public secondary schools in Kipipiri sub-county Nyandarua County in Kenya.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Academic burnout is a students' feeling of frustration, mental exhaustion and lack of motivation towards academics activities. It may lead to reduced productivity and negative attitude towards learning and the school work. There are a number of studies on academic burnout and other related variables that have been studied in Kenya such as academic resilience, social support, learning environment but still academic burnout continue to be a major challenge in the educational setting. The persistency of this problem calls for further study on different variables that might account for academic burnout among students.

Academic burnout is not an exception among learners studying in secondary schools in Kipipiri a sub-county in Nyandarua County. The low academic performance in this sub-county in comparison to other sub-counties of Nyandarua County may be attributed to academic burnout. Moreover, different studies that correlate academic grit on academic burnout are scarce in this county. This variable might act as inhibitor of academic burnout among study population. It is for this reason therefore, that the researcher carried out the current study to establish whether academic engagement relate with academic burnout among learners in form three in Kipipiri a sub-county in Nyandarua County, Kenya.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The Relationship between Academic Engagement and Academic Burnout

Several researches have linked academic engagement to academic burnout. In China Wang et al. (2021) did a study with an aim of finding out whether students' engagements in academic and psychological capital were predicted by academic burnout. Among the participants were the students pursuing nursing course in colleges. Cross-section descriptive survey design guided the study. The participants of the reviewed research were obtained by use of convenience a method of sampling. A total of 733 students were sampled by the researcher for the purpose of data gathering. Four instruments that were modified from Maslach academic burnout and academic engagement scale were applied for measuring academic burnout and academic engagement constructs respectively. Social demographic questionnaire was used to gather data on gender and age of

students pursuing nursing course while psychological capital scale was used to gather data on psychological capital variables. From the analysed data, it was found that academic engagement and psychological capital had a negative association with academic burnout. However, this study used convenience sampling which is prone to biasness in selecting participants whereas the current study aimed to select the participants by the use of simple random sampling.

In a similar work of research in Turkey by Turabik et al. (2019) among students in different faculty in University, the researcher reported that academic engagement had negative relationship with academic burnout. The study was done using a sample size of 472 participants among them 149 male students and 323 female who volunteered to participate for the study. The age bracket for the sample participants was 18 – 42 in terms of years. The research used correlational survey design. Data on academic engagement was collected using students' academic engagement scale while that of burnout was collected by applying Maslach burnout scale. The researcher in attempt to identify the strength of relationship attached to students' academic engagement and burnout, the person correlation coefficient method of data analysis was used for that purpose. The result finding indicated that the correlation between the two variables was negative ($r=-.45, p=.01$). However, the researcher in the reviewed study only included students who volunteered to participate for the research. The current study involved the participants who were sampled randomly.

In South Africa, Brittany at al. (2019) did a study with intent to establish the extent to which burnout and engagement in academic relates. The researcher study participants' were university students pursuing courses in the field of social work. The research was descriptive in terms of design. The population in terms of size of the sample was 43 students who were sampled using convenient sampling techniques. The academic burnout construct was measured using Maslach burnout survey scale while the levels of academic engagement that is vigor, absorption and dedication were measured using Utrecht work engagement scale. The result from the analysed data revealed that students who had low level of cynicism had high level of academic dedication and students with high efficacy had high level of academic vigor and absorption. However, the foregoing reviewed study used descriptive design that limits use of statistical test while making inferences but the current study employed correlational research design which permit making of statistical inferences.

In Ethiopia, Kassie and Alene (2017) sought to establish the relationship between academic engagements, locus of control, coping strategies, academic burnout on achievement in academic work. The research was done among students in Gondor University. The researcher utilized correlational survey design in establishing the relationship between variables studied. In addition, the researcher was interested in grouping the students on the basis of their gender and faculty

therefore stratified techniques in sampling were used for that purpose. Further, the researcher wanted all the students who were interested in participating in the study to have fair chance for participation and therefore, simple random a method in sampling was deemed fit and later was applied. The reviewed research involved 500 learners during data gathering. Raw data was gathered by administering self-report questionnaires to the sample participants that is the Maslach burnout and academic engagement scales to measure academic burnout and academic engagement variables respectively. Data collected was analyzed using varied statistical techniques that were suitable and appropriate for the study. The outcome from the analysed data indicated that the relationship that existed between learners' engagement in academics and that of burnout was a negative. However, this study was done among undergraduate students thus it was important to have another study to examine weather similar findings would be realized if academic engagement was correlated with academic burnout and when students in the level of secondary schools were involved.

In Kenya, the study done by Kay and Wanjohi (2015) investigated academic burnout in relation to study engagement among students in selected universities. The researcher utilized cross sectional design whereas the sample involved for the purpose of gathering data was 105 students. Maslach academic burnout scale was adapted to help measure the levels of academic burnout that may have existed among the students. The construct of academic engagement was measured using work engagement scale. Methods of data correlation that were regarded to be appropriate by the researcher for the study were employed in analyzing the data that was collected. The result indicated that the variables that were under study related negatively. The researcher also was interested in finding the correlation that gender would have on academic burnout. It was revealed that female students had high academic burnout in comparison with male students. In addition, the researcher found that academic burnout coping strategies among them academic grit are important in dealing with academic stress and reduced motivation in academic engagement. The reviewed study was conducted using a sample from university students and hence prompting a need to involve students in secondary schools from Kipipiri Sub-county to establish the extent to which academic engagement correlate with academic burnout.

Masila (2022) in a study that was carried in Machokos County in Kenya, sought to establish the relationship between academic engagement, approaches used in learning and academic achievement. The reviewed work was anchored by engagement and socio-cognitive theories. The researcher used 417 students as a sample size. Self –report questionnaires were administered to the sample participants for data collection. The gathered information was coded and later proper analysis was done. The outcomes from the current study under review revealed that learners who

are engaged in academic perform better in academics. However, the foregoing study correlated academic engagement with academic achievement whereas the researcher in current study correlated academic engagement with academic burnout.

4. METHODOLOGY

Research Design: The researcher in this study was guided by the correlational design in determining the relationship available between academic engagement and academic burnout. The design is deemed appropriate as it enable the researcher to establish the degree to which variables under study is related. This can be done without manipulating itn(Frankel et al. 2015). Therefore, this design was used to reveal the degree of association between academic engagement and academic burnout.

Sampling Techniques and Sample size:

A number of sampling methods were utilized in this study. That is purposive, proportionate and simple random. In choosing Kipipiri Sub-county, the researcher was helped by Purposive sampling because of low academic achievement experienced in this sub-county. The researcher hypothesized that the low academic achievement is attributed to students' academic burnout. Also, purposive sampling was utilized for the purpose of selecting students from form three classes. This is because they were more likely to be affected by academic burnout due to academic pressure as the next candidate class and they were expected to score good grades in their final examination. Proportionate sampling was used to guide in determining appropriate number of schools per category that would participate in the study as shown in table 1.

The researcher was required to have suitable number of students that would make the sample for the research. To achieve this, the researcher used Morgan and Krejcie (1970) sample size determination table. From the table, a population of 1,152 produces a sample size of 291. This is equal to 11% of the total population which is appropriate in accordance with recommendation that was made by Gorard (2003). The recommendation was that a sample that is more than 10% of the total population is ideal to be used in any particular study. To cater for the non-response participants in this study, the researcher added 58 students which were 20% of the actual sample size (291). This was in line with Draugalis et al. (2008) who recommend that a sample size of 10% to 20% should be added to the exact sample size to cater for the participants who may not be present during collection of data. Therefore, a sample of 349 respondents was regarded to be suitable by the researcher. Table 1 indicates the size of the sample and the sampling frame.

Table 1: Sample size and Sampling Frame

School Category	No of Schools	Sample size	Size of the Population	Sample Size of
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in each	per Category	Students		
	Category	Schools		
Boys boarding	2	1	110	33
Girls boarding	2	1	126	38
Mixed day	14	4	508	154
Mixed day boarding	6	2	409	124
Total	24	8	1,152	349

Source: Researcher (2022)

Table 1 shows 1 boy's (33 participants) and 1 girls' (38 participants) boarding schools were sampled. Four mixed day secondary schools with 154 participants were also sampled. Further, two mixed boarding secondary schools with 124 participants were also sampled for the study. Eight secondary schools were chosen with a population of 349 respondents.

Research Instruments: The current study adapted two questionnaires: The Utrecht work engagement scale meant for students by Shaufeli et al. (2006) and Oldenburg burnout academic scale (Demerouti et al. 2003).

Data Collection: The researcher requested for the permit to carry out the research which was granted. This ushered in the process of data collection by the researcher printing the required number of questionnaires. Later, appointment from the principals was sought in order to collect data from the selected schools. The researcher collected data by administering the questionnaires to the selected participants. Data collection was done by the researcher administering the questionnaires to the participants. This was done during official school day and in normal class lesson. This process only took 45 minutes. The collected data from the participants' questionnaires were then compiled and data analysis process followed.

Data Analysis: The collected data was keyed in the computer after the researcher coded it. Data cleaning followed with intent to detect any omitted data or whether there were errors that might have occurred during keying in of data. The researcher used SPSS software to analysis data. Demographic data were analysed using descriptive statistics. Finally, the researcher used appropriate inferential procedures to test the null hypotheses.

FINDINGS

Demographic Information of the Respondents

The researcher administered 349 questionnaires to students from boys boarding, girls boarding, mixed day, and mixed day and boarding schools as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Age and Gender of the Respondents

		Gender		Total
		Male	Female	
Age bracket	14-17	108(31%)	114(33%)	222(64%)
	18-21	46(13%)	46(13%)	92(27%)
	22 Above	10(3%)	21(6%)	31(9%)
Total		164(48%)	181(52%)	345(98.9%)

Note: N= 345

In terms of gender, majority of the respondents (52%) were female while male respondents were 48%. In terms of age, most of the respondents (64%) were aged between 14-17 years, then they were followed by those between age 18-21 at 27%, and lastly those aged 22 and above at 9%.

Descriptive Statistics of Academic Burnout

The scores of academic burnout were analysed using descriptive statistics. The result is indicated in table 6.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of Academic Burnout

	N	Range	Min	Max	M	SD	Sk	Kur
Academic Burnout	345	31.00	29.00	60.00	40.93	4.05	.41	1.66

Note. N = 345

The minimum score was 29.00 while the maximum score was 60.00 giving a range of 31.00. The mean score stood at 40.93 with a standard deviation of 4.05. Normality was assessed by using the coefficients of skewness and kurtosis, Sk = -.41, Kur = 1.66 and the assumption was met. The skewness value was below 2 and kurtosis value was below 3, indicating normal distribution.

The descriptive statistics of academic burnout by school category were also obtained. The result was indicated in table 4.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics of Academic Burnout by School Category

Type of school	N	Min	Max	Range	M	SD
Boys Boarding	33	34.00	53.00	19.00	40.12	4.16

Girls Boarding	38	33.00	50.00	17.00	40.64	4.25
Mixed Day	152	31.00	49.00	18.00	41.81	3.56
Mixed day and boarding	122	29.00	60.00	31.00	42.03	4.49
Total	345	29.00	60.00	31.00	40.93	4.05

Note. $N = 345$

The mixed day and boarding schools obtained the highest mean score of 42.03 with a standard deviation of 4.49. Their minimum score was 29.00 while their maximum score was 60.00, giving a range of 31. The mixed day schools followed with a mean score of 41.81 with a standard deviation of 3.56. Their minimum score was 31.00 while their maximum was 49.00, giving a range of 18. The girls' boarding schools followed with a mean score of 40.64 with a standard deviation of 4.25. Their minimum score was 33.00 while their maximum was 50.00, giving a range of 17. The least mean score was obtained by boys' boarding schools with a mean score of 40.12 with a standard deviation of 4.16. Their minimum score was 34.00 while their maximum was 53.00, giving a range of 19.

Scores for academic burnout among the students were categorized into low, and high. The frequencies of these levels of academic burnout were obtained. The result is given in table 5.

Table 5: Levels of Academic Burnout

	Frequency	Percent
Low	98	28.4
High	247	71.6
Total	345	100.0

Note: $N=345$

A majority of the respondents (71.6%), had high academic burnout. Those with low academic burnout scored 28.4%.

Hypothesis testing

In regards to this objective that make this study, it was intended to determine the relationship between academic engagement and academic burnout. The hypothesis that was formulated is as follows:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between academic engagement and academic burnout among form three students.

This hypothesis was tested by use of bivariate correlation analysis that employed the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. The table labeled 6 shows the outcome from the analysis.

Table 6: Correlation between Academic Engagement and Academic Burnout

		Academic Burnout
Academic Engagement	Pearson Correlation	-.68**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.00
	N	345

Note: N =345

The results presented in Table 6, show that there was a strong, negative, and statistically significant relationship between academic engagement and academic burnout, $r(345) = -.68, p < .05$. These results indicate that an increase in the level of student academic engagement resulted in a significant decrease in students' academic burnout. This was not in agreement with the null hypothesis, and as such, the null hypothesis was rejected because the p obtained was less than the set level of significance (.05). It was therefore concluded that academic engagement was significantly related to students' academic burnout.

Further, the relationship between the three sub domains of (academic engagement vigor, academic engagement dedication and academic engagement absorption) and academic burnout were examined. The product moment correlation was utilized for this function and the findings are shown from the table labeled 7.

Table 7: Correlation between Academic Engagement Sub Domains and Academic Burnout

		Academic Burnout
Ac. Eng –Vigor	Pearson Correlation	-.67**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.00
	N	345
Ac. Eng_Dedication	Pearson Correlation	-.78**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.00
	N	345
Ac. Eng_Absorption	Pearson Correlation	-.62**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.00
	N	345

Note. Ac.Eng – Academic engagement

As indicated in Table 7, academic engagement vigor score had a strong, negative and significant relationship with academic burnout, $r(345) = -.67, p < .05$. The results suggest that the higher the

academic engagement vigor, the lower the academic burnout. Regarding the sub domain of academic engagement dedication, there was a strong negative and significant relationship with academic burnout, $r(345) = -.78, p < .05$. Similarly, academic engagement absorption depict strong negative and significant relationship with academic burnout, $r(345) = -.62, p < .05$. The results show that students with high levels of academic engagement vigor, high level of academic engagement dedication and high level of academic engagement absorption suffered less academic burnout.

Having confirmed that there exists a significant relationship between academic engagement sub domains and academic burnout, the prediction values of academic engagement vigor, academic engagement dedication, and academic engagement absorption on academic burnout were computed. The outcomes are as per the given table 8

Table 8: Model Summary for Prediction of Academic Burnout from Academic Engagement Sub Domains

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.79 ^a	.62	.62	2.49

a. Predictors: (Constant), Ac_Eng_Absorption, Ac_Eng_Dedication, Ac_Eng_Vigor

b. Dependent Variable: Academic Burnout

As shown in Table 8, R square value was 0.62 which indicates that 62% of the variance in academic burnout among form three students in Kipipiri Sub-county, Kenya is jointly influenced by academic engagement vigor, academic engagement dedication and academic engagement absorption. The rest may be explained by other factors that were not considered in this study. The multiple regression coefficients were .79 which indicates a high correlation between academic engagement vigor, academic engagement dedication and academic engagement absorption and academic burnout.

ANOVA test was used to determine if this joint influence of academic burnout by the three academic engagement sub domains was significant. Table 9 presents the results as follows

Table 9: ANOVA in the Prediction of Academic Burnout

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
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	Regression	3525.82	3	1175.27	188.82	.00 ^b
1	Residual	2122.51	341	6.22		
	Total	5648.33	344			

a. Dependent Variable: Academic Burnout

b. Predictors: (Constant), Ac_Eng_Absorption, Ac_Eng_Dedication, Ac_Eng_Vigor

The results in table 9 reveals that three academic engagement sub domains had a joint significant relationship with academic burnout of form three students in Kipipiri Sub-county, Kenya, $F(3, 341) = 188.82, p < .05$. This implies that academic engagement vigor, academic engagement dedication and academic engagement absorption significantly predict academic burnout.

DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

The researcher in the first objective of this study intended to establish the relationship that existed between academic engagement and academic burnout among form three students in Kipipiri Sub-County. It was found that the two variables had negative and significant relationship. This translates that increases in the level of student academic engagement result in a significant decrease in students' academic burnout. From the descriptive statistics, the mean score of 28.93 leaned towards the maximum score of 43 than it did towards the minimum score of 9. The descriptive statistics for academic burnout revealed a mean score of 40.93 which was near average. This revealed that a considerable number of students were experiencing academic burnout. There is a need therefore for the students to balance between classwork and other social activities to address the issue of academic burnout. When the relationship between the sub domains of (academic engagement vigor, academic engagement dedication and academic engagement absorption) and academic burnout were examined using product moment correlation, it was established that academic engagement vigor score had a strong, negative and significant relationship with academic burnout, $r(345) = -.67, p < .05$.

These results suggest that when academic engagement vigor becomes higher, the academic burnout tend to decline and vice versa. In respect to the sub domain of academic engagement dedication, there was a strong negative and significant relationship with academic burnout, $r(345) = -.78, p < .05$. This suggests that when there is higher academic engagement dedication, lower academic burnout is experienced and vice versa. Similarly, in respect to the last sub domain of academic engagement absorption, there was a strong negative and significant association with academic burnout, $r(345) = -.62, p < .05$. This result suggests that when the academic engagement absorption rises, the academic burnout become lower and vice versa. This means that students with

high levels of academic engagement vigor, raised academic engagement dedication and high level of academic engagement absorption suffered less academic burnout and vice versa. The three sub domain results confirm that there exists a significant relationship between academic engagement and academic burnout.

The predictive values of academic engagement vigor, academic engagement dedication and academic engagement absorption on academic burnout were significant. The outcomes in terms of findings embedded in this study are supported by work engagement theory by Shaufeli et al. (2002), who proposed that in line with psychological point of view, activities that are done by students including attending classes are considered as work. This is considered in the sense that academic work is goal oriented towards exceling in examinations.

Work engagement theory by Shaufeli et al. (2002) has engagement divided into three aspects namely, vigor, dedication and absorption which have been used in this study. To begin with, vigor as described in work engagement theory refers to increased energy that enable one to work for more hours without getting exhausted. In academic field and in this study, refers to willingness of a student to exert effort in academic activities, and their persistence in the face of challenges during their studies. The study hypothesized that students with vigor would have low level of academic burnout as they would be believed to approach learning activities positively and with mental resilience. The outcomes attached in this study have worked as reinforcement for this. Secondly, dedication refers to one being focused in work and being inspired to work even if facing challenges.

In the academic field and in this study, students with dedication have been considered likely to be self- inspired and to have a sense of enthusiasm for engaging in studies, which would reduce their eve of academic burnout. This too has been supported by the study results. Lastly, absorption in work engagement theory means one's ability to be engrossed in work to the extent of finding difficult to detach from it. In the academic field and in this study, students with dedication have been considered as those likely to be self-inspired and also having a sense of enthusiasm for engaging in studies. Further, students with absorption were hypothesized to be able to fully concentrate in their academic activities. Such students are expected to have less academic burnout. This too has been supported by the outcomes that have been revealed in the current study.

The study results also are in line with Mae et al. (2022) who in support of work engagement theory explained that students' academic engagement has a rewarding power towards better academic performance and alleviation of academic boredom and burnout. Similarly, the study results agree with findings from research work in Kenya by Kay and Wanjohi (2015) which investigated academic burnout in relation to study engagement among 105 students sampled from selected

universities. The findings revealed that academic engagement and academic burnout had a negative correlation.

From the foregoing, the evidence has revealed that the existing literature from past research has demonstrated that academic engagement enables students to get deeply absorbed in learning activities when interacting with learning materials, with the teachers and with their peers. This engagement draw student into deep thinking by involving themselves in activities like deducing meaning through analyzing and understanding concepts and rationalizing procedures (Amerstorfer & Kistner, 2021). Students who are highly academically engaged are subsequently noted to face less academic burnout. This has been clearly supported by the outcome of the findings in the current research. It is important that education stakeholders and policy makers engage and implement these findings to address the issue of academic burnout in secondary schools. This will enable them to develop strategies that promote high level of academic engagement among students in learning institutions in order to get better learning outcomes.

CONCLUSIONS

The first objective of this research was to determine the relationship between academic engagement and academic burnout among form three students in Kipipiri Sub-county. From the results, the study concludes that there exists a significant negative relationship between academic engagement and academic burnout. This result suggests that an increase in academic engagement would lower academic burnout and vice versa. After examining the relationship between the sub domains of (academic engagement vigor, academic engagement dedication and academic engagement absorption) and academic burnout, the study concludes all the three had a strong, negative and significant relationship with academic burnout. This result suggests that an increase in either of them would lower academic burnout and vice versa. The three sub domain result reaffirms that the correlation that is available between academic engagement and academic burnout is significant.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The study used questionnaires only to collect data from the students. For in-depth understanding of academic burnout, the researcher recommends for a similar study to be conducted using mixed research where both quantitative and qualitative data will be collected in other counties in Kenya. This will help to bring out more issues on academic burnout that cannot be measured using questionnaires.

The study participants were learners in form three in Kipipiri Sub-county in Nyandarua County and therefore there is need for similar studies in other counties involving students in primary, college and university to enhance generalization of the findings. This will go a long to address the issue of academic burnout among students in different levels of learning.

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